

Cyclic Heat Treatment of Carbon Steel

Himanshu Choudhary, Md Shahriar Rokon , Bhaskar Bhallamudi , Sudesh Singh
Department of Mechanical Engineering, SET, Sharda University, Greater Noida, India.

Abstract:- Carbon steel is widely available and affordable, and it possesses all of the material properties required for a variety of applications. Carbon steel is heat treated to increase ductility, toughness, strength, hardness, and tensile strength while also relieving internal stress. The harness and ultimate tensile strength experiment is being conducted in order to get a better knowledge of heat treated low and high carbon steel, which has a wide range of industrial and research uses.

Keywords:- Ductility , Tensile Strength, Internal Stress , Ultimate Tensile Strength.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many technical components undergo heat treatment as part of the final manufacture process. Steel components and tools for sophisticated application can only be given good mechanical characteristics by heat treatment. Heat treatment is a highly essential metallurgical technique for changing the characteristics of steels. If a steel is treated to different heat treatments, it can have a wide variety of mechanical characteristics. Heat treatment is now regarded to be highly essential in the field of material science, where a lot of research is being done in the quest of greater mechanical characteristics . In general, increasing the carbon amount of an alloy from 0.01 to 1.5 percent enhances its strength and hardness, while increasing the carbon content beyond 1.5 percent reduces the steel's ductility and malleability significantly. Ductility is a crucial mechanical feature for steels utilized in applications such as cold and warm deformation, as well as for machinability. The transition of lamellar pearlite to granular pearlite is referred to as spheroidization. As a result, the metal's hardness and strength are greatly reduced, but its ductility improves. The steel industry has faced a hurdle in speeding up the Spheroidization of pearlitic structures, as traditional Spheroidization method of steel, which involves a subcritical annealing treatment, takes a lengthy time. Even after 100 hours of storage at 700°C, the Spheroidization in an annealed Fe–0.79 wt% C alloy remained partial . Isothermal annealing at 680°C in 0.72 percent C steel with fine pearlitic formation takes 72 hours of holding time for approximately 100 percent Spheroidization, whereas 50 hours of holding time only results in 50 percent Spheroidization. As a result, numerous approaches have been devised to speed up Spheroidization, including as;

- Thermal cycling at a temperature close to A_{c1} .
- Before, during, or after the transition of austenite to pearlite, isothermal annealing with cold work
- Before, during, or after the change of austenite to pearlite, hot deformation occurs.

In this work the attention was focused on a relatively new technique of cyclic heat treatment in which the specimen was heated for short duration above A_{c3} temperature for short duration (6 minutes) and followed by forced air cooling to the room temperature. The study was made on two different grades of steels, one was low carbon steel and the other was high carbon steel for different number of heat treatment cycles.

II. HEAT TREATMENT

Heat treatment is basically a process of heating and cooling the material with which the microstructure and mechanical properties are changed. Heat treatment is used to bring about desirable changes in the metallurgical structure and, as a result, in the characteristics of metal components. Most metals and alloys can be affected by heat treatment, but ferrous alloys, particularly steels, see the most drastic changes in characteristics. There are two allotropic states of iron in the solid form. (Allotropy refers to an element's ability to have multiple crystal lattices depending on temperature and pressure.) Iron has a body centered cubic (bcc) lattice and is referred to as α -iron (α -Fe) at low temperatures up to 910°C. At 910 degrees Celsius, α -iron crystals become γ -iron crystals with a face-centered cubic (FCC) structure. The crystals are stable up to 1400 degrees Celsius. Above this temperature, they revert to a bcc lattice and are referred to as δ -iron crystals. The sole difference between δ -iron crystals and α -iron crystals is the temperature range in which they exist. Bcc lattices (α -Fe, δ -Fe) have a lattice constant of 0.286 nm, while FCC lattices (γ -Fe) have a lattice constant of 0.364 nm. α -Fe has a significant ferromagnetic property at low temperatures. When heated to around 770°C, ferromagnetism disappears. This is because the lattice loses its ferromagnetic spin ordering, according to recent research. Above 770°C, the state of iron is known as γ -Fe. The lattice of paramagnetic crystals is the same as the lattice of δ -iron crystals.

Fig. 1-Iron- Carbon diagram in concise view

Carbon percentage is only displayed up to 6% in the phase diagram given that commercially wholesome iron includes up to 0.008% C, steels up to 2.11 percent C, and C.I.s up to 6.67 percent C. 1538° C is the melting point of pure iron. It generates delta ferrite initially, then austenite, and lastly alpha ferrite as it cools. Alpha ferrite, often known as ferrite, is a solid solution of BCC iron with a maximum solid solubility of 0.022 percent C at a temperature of 727°C. Because delta ferrite is only stable at extremely high temperatures, it has no practical utility. Ferrite (from the Latin word ferrum) is a soft, ductile metal that can withstand temperatures of up to 768°C and is magnetic. Between 1394 and 912 degrees Celsius, iron undergoes a change from the BCC to the FCC structure, resulting in gamma iron, also known as Austenite. Austenite has a substantially greater solid solubility than ferrite, up to 2.11 percent Celsius . At higher temperatures, austenite is denser than ferrite and more ductile. The austenitic type of steel is non-magnetic. The hand on the right border of the phase diagram represents cementite, which is 100 percent iron carbide with 6.67 percent carbon. Cementite is an intermetallic compound that is extremely hard and brittle. The following are some of the reactions that occur on the iron carbon phase diagram.

➤ *Eutectoid Reaction*

When iron containing 0.77 percent carbon is cooled from 1100°C in the austenitic phase to 727°C, a reaction

occurs, converting the iron to ferrite (BCC) and cementite. The Eutectoid Reaction is the name given to this reaction. Pearlite is the resulting microstructure of eutectoid steel, which consists of alternate layers of ferrite and cementite. Pearlite's mechanical properties are thus intermediate between those of soft and ductile ferrite and hard and brittle cementite.

➤ *Hypo-eutectoid Steel*

Similarly, at higher temperatures, when the carbon concentration is less than 0.77 percent, the material is totally austenitic, but as it cools, it enters the stable ferrite and austenite area. The austenite is of eutectoid composition and contains 0.77 percent C at 727°C, while the remaining austenite changes into pearlite after further cooling. Proeutectoid ferrite and pearlite are the end products.

➤ *Hyper-eutectoid Steel*

The proeutectoid phase of steel having more than 0.76 percent C is ferrite rather than austenite when cooled. The remaining austenite loses carbon content as the carbon-rich phase evolves, reaching eutectoid composition at 727°C. Below 727°C, all residual austenite converts into pearlite. The resultant structure has a continuous cementite network, making the material very fragile.

Fig.2- Iron Carbon Diagram (in depth)

Phase (microconstituents)	Crystal structure of phases	Characteristics
Ferrite (α -iron)	bcc	Low-temperature phase that is rather soft, with a stable equilibrium phase.
δ -ferrite (δ -iron)	bcc	High-temperature phase; stable equilibrium phase; isomorphous with -iron
Austenite (γ -iron)	fcc	Medium-temperature phase that is rather soft; stable equilibrium phase
Cementite (Fe_3C)	Complex orthorhombic	Phase of hard metastability
Graphite	Hexagonal	Phase of stable equilibrium
Pearlite		Microconstituent that is metastable; a lamellar combination of ferrite and cementite.
Martensite	bct (supersaturated solution of carbon in ferrite)	Hard metastable phase; lath morphology when 0.6 wt% C; plate morphology when >1.0 wt% C; and a combination of both when >1.0 wt% C
Bainite		Lower bainite created at lower temperatures has an acicular look; upper bainite formed at higher temperatures has a feathery appearance; upper bainite formed at higher temperatures has a nonlamellar blend of ferrite and cementite on an exceedingly thin scale. The hardness of bainite rises as the temperature of production decreases.

Table 1-different crystal structures phases associated with phases

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Experiment was performed on two different grades of steels one is low carbon steel and the other was high carbon steel. The carbon contents of the two steels are given below

- 0.24% wt. Carbon steel
- 0.65% wt. Carbon steel

Material was supplied in the form of 10 mm diameter rods. These rods are cut in a length of 120 mm to make the samples for the experiment. From each steel five samples are prepared. These samples are subjected to different number of heat treatment cycles viz. 0, 1, 3, 5, 7. And the Samples are prepared from two different grades of steels viz. one from low carbon steel and another from high carbon steel. First samples from both the materials are homogenized at a temperature of 1000°C for one and half hour in electric resistance furnace. By homogenizing the previous history of the samples are eliminated. After homogenizing the both steel samples are subjected to heat treatment for spheroidizing treatment. The design of Heat treatment cycle is as follows The experiment was designed to heat the samples in the austenitizing range for short duration. Here proper time is not given to the samples for completely austenitizing. So in this experiment

the steel sample are heated around 50°C above the A_{c3} temp. For short duration 6 minutes and cooling to the room temp. By forced air cooling in 8 minutes. Thus a single heat treatment cycle takes 14 minutes. So first the A_{c3} temp. is calculated for both the steel samples.

For 0.24% wt. C steel A_{c3} temp. is 820°C so the selected temp. is 50°C above this temp. $820 + 50 = 870^\circ\text{C}$ is taken. For 0.65% wt. C steel A_{c3} temp. is 750°C so the selected temp. is 50°C above this temp. $750 + 50 = 800^\circ\text{C}$ is taken. The samples were prepared by cutting a small part of heat treated metal from some location of test bar. The samples were prepared with the help of wheel-grinder and belt-grinder then polished by using different grades of emery paper followed by cloth polishing. After that the micro structural images are captured with the help of a digital microscope. Un-etched and etched samples were seen in digital microscope and images were captured for different number of treatment cycles. Microstructure was seen in image analyzer with and without etching (5 % initial) and image of microstructure was taken. An optical microscope with an image analyzer was used for micro-examination and phase analysis. ASTM E562.32 was used to determine the proportion of phases contained in the microstructure. All the samples were examined with 100X

magnification. For hardness test we have used Brinelli method. Each sample was subjected to a hardness test using a Brinell hardness testing equipment. The Brinell hardness test involves pressing a 10mm diameter hardened steel into the test material with a 3000kg weight. The weight can be reduced to 1500kg or 500kg for softer materials to reduce excessive indentation. The total load is normally applied for 10 to 15 seconds in the case of iron and steel. A low-powered microscope was used to measure the diameter of the indentation left in the test material. From the BHN data table, the hardness value of the appropriate diameter of indentation was noted. Three distinct BHN values were obtained in three different spots on the sample, and the average of all BHN values was determined for all samples. Tensile testing was performed using a universal tensile testing equipment. The tensile test is a test that is nearly widely used to represent mechanical characteristics and to provide the most basic information about material behaviour. Two gauge markings are made lengthwise on the specimen before the test begins. The test piece's ends are then grasped in the tensile testing machine, and the load is steadily increased until failure is reached. Extensometers measure the amount of elongation in the test piece generated by the load. Loads and deformation data are kept track of while the test component is loaded.

$$\text{Ultimate Strength} = \frac{\text{maximum load}}{\text{original cross-sectional area}}$$

$$\text{Yield strength} = \frac{\text{yield point load}}{\text{original cross sectional area}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Percentage elongation} = \frac{\text{final length} - \text{inatial length}}{\text{inital length}} \times 100$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *For low carbon steel*

Sample the heat treatment temperture is 870°C is used. This temperature is above the Ac₃ temperture where the α-iron changes into the γ-iron. This transformation is actually a diffusionless transformation phenomena which occurs at very high speed. As a result, either the proeutectoid ferrite area or eutectodal ferrite, such as the ferrite found in pearlite, swiftly converts to austenite. At high power points, for instance the particle border of ferrite, the crossing point pearlite colony, and the ferrite granule, proeutectoud ferrite begins to transition to austenite (with nucleation of fine austenite grains). The interface between the pearlite colony and the ferrite grain, in particular, is said to be a possible location for austenitization because the cementite decomposition adds carbon to the alteration face, reducing the revolution temperature. As a result, either the proeutectoid ferrite area or eutectodal ferrite, such as the ferrite found in pearlite, swiftly converts to austenite. At elevated energy points, for instance the grain boundary of ferrite, the border pearlite colony, and the ferrite grain, proeutectoud ferrite begins to transition to austenite (with nucleation of fine austenite grains). The interface between the pearlite outpost and the ferrite grain, in particular, is said to be a possible location for austenitization

because the cementite breakdown adds carbon to the alteration face, reducing the alteration temperature.

Number of Heat Treatment cycles		Hardness (BHN)	
1.	0	1.	95.5
2.	1	2.	103
3.	3	3.	107
4.	5	4.	106
5.	7	5.	104

Table 2- Number of Heat Treatment cycles and Hardness for Low Carbon steel (BHN)

Fig 3. Graph showing Hardness vs No. of Heat Treatment Cycles.

The hardness initially increases upto 3 number of cycles. Then it starts decreasing for higher number of cycles viz. 5, 7. As the the hardness decreases ductility increases. The grain refining causes the initial rise in hardness and after that it starts decreasing because of change of lamellar cementite to spheroidal cementite. So it is concluded that the ductility initially decreases then it starts increasing. These samples have low strength and high ductlity, which is well known property of low carbon steel.

Tensile Strength Properties of Low Carbon Steel samples as follows are summarized in the following table

Fig 4- A Graph showing Propersties vs No. of Heat Treatment Cycles.

Fig 5 – A graph showing elongation in percentage vs No. of Heat Treatment Cycles.

Table shows the relationship between mechanical qualities and the number of heat treatment cycles, with a graph. The strength qualities (ultimate tensile strength and yield strength) rise during the first 5 heat treatment cycles before declining. As a result, the ductility attribute (percent elongation) drops at first and then increases. Following the recognized features of low carbon steel, the homogenizing annealed 0.3 percent C steel example has low strength and high ductility.

➤ *For High Carbon Steel*

The optical and SEM micrographs depict the morphologies. The samples with varying numbers of heat treatment cycles are shown in SEM photographs. The ferrite contained in the first example is eutectoid ferrite within the pearlite, whereas the remaining ferrite is proeutectoid ferrite. The cementite is only found in the lamellar form within the pearlite in the original sample, which has had no heat treatment cycles. However, as demonstrated in the micrographs, lamellar pearlite decreases and spheroidal cementite rises as the number of heat treatment cycles increases. After seven heat treatment cycles, the microstructure consists mostly of cementite spheroids and ferrite, with traces of lamellar cementite. According to 'fault migration theory,' the main mechanism of classic subcritical isothermal spheroidization involves atomic diffusion from highly curved lamellar fault sites to surrounding boring flat surfaces. As a result, the current work amplifies another high-temperature diffusional process, namely the diffusion of atoms from lamellar fault sites to neighboring austenite during austenitization. Furthermore, it is recognized that non-equilibrium forced air cooling causes greater structural flaws. As a result, fine pearlite generated by forced air cooling (non-equilibrium cooling) is more likely to have more lamellar fault sites (defect enriched regions) on cementite lamellae in subsequent heat treatment cycles, hastening the Spheroidization process. The spheroids begin to grow in size after a higher number of heat treatment cycles (5 cycles), and the microstructure largely consists of isolated cementite

spheroids and ferrite after 7 cycles of heat treatment. The total time necessary to complete seven heat treatment cycles is as regards 1 hour and 38 minutes. Spheroidization in the ordinary subcritical state takes substantially longer (about 100 h).

➤ *Number of Heat Treatment cycles and Hardness for High Carbon Steel (BHN)*

Fig 6- A graph showing Number of Heat Treatment cycles vs Hardness (BHN)

The hardness initially increases upto 5 number of cycles. Then it starts decreasing for higher number of cycles viz. 7. The primary raise in the hardness is suitable to the grain refinement. Once the change of lamellar cementite to the spheroidal cementite begins the hardness starts decreasing. As the the hardness decreases ductility increases. So it is concluded that the ductility initially decreases then it starts increasing. This sample has low strength and high ductility, which is well known property of low carbon steel.

➤ *Tensile Strength Properties of High Carbon Steel*

The results are summarized in the following table.

➤ *Results from Tensile Test for High Carbon Steel*

No. of Heat Treatment Cycles	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	% Elongation
0	360	580	12
1	385	624	10
3	440	680	8
5	495	770	8
7	445	721	9.5

Table 3- Showing results from Tensile Test for High Carbon Steel

Fig 7- Graph showing UTS , YS vs Number of Heat Treatment Cycles for High Carbon Steel

Fig 8- A graph showing elongation vs Number of Heat Treatment Cycles

V. CONCLUSIONS

From above results and discussions following conclusions may be drawn:

- Spheroidization in the ordinary subcritical state takes substantially longer (about 100 h). The total time necessary to complete seven heat treatment cycles is about 1 hour and 38 minutes. Hence this process is fast process of Spheroidization.
- Hardness initially increases due to grain refinement but due to change of lamellar cementite into spheroids of cementite hardness decreases. The ductility initially increases and after that it increases.

- Finally, the microstructure consists largely solitary cementite spheroids and ferrite after 7 cycles of heat treatment.
- The process is more effective for high carbon steel than low carbon steel due to its poor response to the heat treatment.
- The microstructure consists generally of cementite spheroids and ferrite with traces of lamellar cementite after 7 heat treatment cycles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to Sharda University, Greater Noida, for providing computational support through Sharda Seed Money.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Steel Booklet , Material Science Mech- 2014.
- [2]. Nandita Gupta and S.K. Sen, "Spheroidisation Treatment for Steels" Defence Science Journal, Vol. 56, No. 4, October 2006, pp. 665-676.
- [3]. Y.L. Tian, R.W. Kraft, Metall. Trans. A18A (1987) 1403-1414.
- [4]. D.K. Mondal, R.M. Dey, Trans. IIM 37 (1984) 351-356.
- [5]. Material Science And Engineering, 4th Edition, V.Raghavan, p. 396.
- [6]. T.V. Rajan, C.P.Sharma, Ashok Sharma, Heat Treatment Principles and Techniques. "Heat Treatment Processes for Steels" Chapter 5 pg. no. 86-107.
- [7]. William D. Callister , Material Science and Engineering An Introduction, "Phase Transformation in Materials" Chapter 11 pg. no. 311-357.
- [8]. Physical Metallurgy- Vijendar Singh.
- [9]. O'Brien, James &Hosford, Willium F. Spheroidisation cycles for medium carbon steels. Metallur.Mater. Trans. A, April 2002, 33A, 1255.
- [10]. Paquetion, H. &Pineau, A. Acceleration of pearlite spheroidization by thermomechanical treatment. J. Iron Steel Inst., Dec 1971, 991.
- [11]. Aihara, K. A new thermomechanical processing for spheroidizing carbide directly in a rolling line.In 33rd MWSP Conference Proceedings, ISS-AIME, 1992, 29, 285.
- [12]. O'Brien, J.M. &Hosford, Willium F.Spheroidisation of medium-carbon steels. J. Mater. Engg.Perform., Feb 1997, 6(1), 69.
- [13]. AtanuSaha, Dipak Kumar Mondal, Koushik Biswas, JoydeepMaity, "Microstructural modifications and changes in mechanical properties during cyclic heat treatment of 0.16% carbon steel" Materials Science and Engineering A 534 (2012) 465- 475.
- [14]. AtanuSaha, Dipak Kumar Mondal, Koushik Biswas, JoydeepMaity, "Development of high strength ductile hypereutectoid steel by cyclic heat treatment process" Materials Science and Engineering A 541 (2012) 204-215.

- [15]. Z.Q.Lv , B.Wang, Z.H.Wang, S.H.Sun , W.T.Fu, “Effect of cyclic heat treatments on spheroidizing behavior of cementite in high carbon steel” *Materials Science & Engineering A* 574 (2013) 143–148.
- [16]. VivekanandSista, Philip Nash, Satyam S. SahayJ, “Accelerated bainitic transformation during cyclic austempering” *Mater Sci* (2007) 42:9112–9115.
- [17]. Mahdi MUHAMMADPOUR, Ali-Reza KIANI-RASHID, “AN ACCELERATED SPHEROIDIZATION METHOD IN HIGH CHROMIUM TOOL STEEL” 21. - 22. 11. 2012, Plzeň, Czech Republic, EU.
- [18]. V.A. Baranova, G.D. Sukhomlin, *MetallovedenieiTermicheskayarabotkaMetallov* 11 (1981) 51–55.
- [19]. K. K. Alaneme, O. J. Adejumo, J. O. Borode, “INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT CYCLIC INTERCRITICALHEATTREATMENT SCHEDULES ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF A DUAL PHASE MEDIUM CARBON LOW ALLOY STEEL”*Association of Metallurgical Engineers of Serbia (AMES),Scientific paper UDC: 669.14.*
- [20]. *Introduction to Tensile Testing, CHAPTER 1, 2004 ASM International.*
- [21]. <http://www.osti.gov/scitech/servlets/purl/836878>